

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF A MANUAL THRESHER FOR RUBBER SEEDS PROCESSING AND STORAGE

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ABSTRACT

The development and evaluation of a manual rubber threshing machine was carried out with a view to reducing the drudgery and losses attached to threshing of rubber seeds for further processing and storage. The machine comprises of a concave sieve, frame, threshing arms and side plates. The aperture of the concave sieve was designed based on the dimensions of some collected samples of rubber seeds. The performance of the machine was evaluated using three runs of rubber seeds at 2kg per run at 9.307% moisture content wet basis. The results showed the average threshing efficiency of 90.83 %, average percentage of unthreshed rubber seed of 2.167 %, average percentage of semi-threshed of 7% and average throughput capacity of 53.4kg/hr as the performance indices. It can be concluded, that the developed machine performed efficiently.

Keywords: Rubber threshing machine, development, evaluation, efficiency, throughput capacity.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Rubber crop (*Hevea brasiliensis*) as presented in Plate 1 is a crop known for its common products: rubberwood, rubber milk or latex, rubber honey and more recently, rubber seed oil. It remains the world's primary source of natural rubber (Nosa, 2018). In Nigeria, Rubber is an important economic crop which has a diversity of applications, such as serving as source of raw materials for agro-based industries, generating foreign exchange and providing employment opportunities. Rubber is valued for its elastic behavior, or deformation by contraction or expansion which makes it ideal for use in the tyre industry. It is predominantly used for manufacturing high-speed, heavy-

duty, and radial tyres, due to its low heat build-up and excellent tear strength. Beyond tyre production, rubber is used for the production of specific products such as flexible oil-resistant pipelines for offshore oil fields, inner tubes of tyres, footwear, bridge pads, and building foundations in earthquake-prone areas (Fagbemi *et al*, 2014).

The rubber tree bears fruit when at four years of age. Each fruit contains three or four seeds, and a mature tree yields about 800 seeds (approximately 1.3 kg) twice a year. Each seed consists of a thin, hard shell and shiny brown or grey to brown with numerous darker mottles or streaks on its coat, and a kernel containing oil. A typical rubber seed weighs between 3.5 - 6.0 g, average weight of the dried seed is about 4.5 g, and the kernel of the rubber seed is roughly half the weight of the total seed (Aigbodion *et al*, 2005).

Rubber is vital in the socio-economic life of many tropical developing nations, including Nigeria. In Nigeria, rubber tree flowers once in a year, which is between February and March, while in one of the leading rubber producers, Malaysia, its flowering occurs twice a year, between March and April, and between August and September (Fagbemi *et al*, 2014). Rubber seed have industrial value, being used in the manufacture of putty and alkyd resins, which find application in the paint and leather industry. The seed oil, rich in fatty acids, 23% oleic, 32.5% linoleic, and 22.5% linoleic, is useful in production biodiesel, cosmetics, and food products due to its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Nigeria has approximately 247,100 hectares of land under rubber cultivation, of which more than half is owned by small-scale farmers (Mesike and Esekade 2014). The country is projected to have a yield of 43,000 tonnes of rubber seeds, which, if properly harnessed, will add value to the downstream sector of the rubber industry in the provision of employment through seed collection and processing.

To reduce losses, drudgery and add value to the rubber industry, there is a need for research on rubber seed processing mechanization, particularly in the area of threshing, because the current practice, which involves crude manual cracking method, is labor-intensive and inefficient.

This study aims to design and fabricate a manual threshing machine for rubber seed to facilitate the removal of seed coat, thereby improving kernel recovery. The ultimate objective is to enhance the rubber seed recovery by providing a low-cost and accessible mechanical solution for the small-scale processors.

Plate 1: Rubber Seeds

2.0 METHODOLOGY

The machine was designed to be simple, easily maintained and of low cost. The major components of the machine are the threshing arm, the threshing chamber, the concave sieve and the main frame of the machine. The following were considered while developing the machine:

- i. Physical and mechanical properties of the rubber seeds.
- ii. Availability of materials.
- iii. Cost of the materials.
- iv. Maintenance of the machine.
- v. Reproducibility of the machine.
- vi. Concave clearance between the threshing arm and the sieve.
- vii. Mobility of the machine.
- viii. Ease of operation.

2.1 Description of Machine Components

This section provides a detailed description of the various components that makes up the rubber seed thresher.

2.1.1 Threshing Chamber

As shown in Figure 2, this is where the threshing operation takes place. It also functions as the hopper of the machine since the rubber seeds to be threshed will also be introduced into this component.

2.1.2 Threshing Arm

As presented in Figure 2, it is made up of the handle, threshing shaft, and shoes. The handle acts as a fulcrum where the force used to thresh the rubber seeds is supplied by the operator. The handle

is attached to a series of bars to form an arrangement where the shoes will be attached and the shoes made from cast iron produces the frictional and rubbing force that threshes the rubber seeds.

2.1.3 Concave Sieve

As presented in Figure 2, the concave sieve acts in conjunction with the threshing arm to break the rubber seeds. It also has aperture relative to the dimensions of the rubber seeds and will only allow the cracked seed coats and kernel to pass through its holes.

2.1.4 Frame

The frame as shown in Figure 2 forms the structure of the machine and is responsible for bearing the loads acting on the machine as a result of its components and feed materials.

2.2 Components Design.

This section details the design calculations of the various components of the machine.

2.2.1 Threshing Chamber.

In the design of the threshing chamber the following points were considered:

- i. The machine will be manually operated
- ii. The machine should be able to thresh at least 15 kg in a single unit operation.
- iii. Allowances to allow for ease of operation.
- iv. The threshing chamber will be semi-circular while the arm will be circular to allow more surface area contact with the rubber seeds.
- v. The height of the threshing chamber will be 0.215 m for material use efficiency, portability and mobility.

Taking into consideration the quantity of feed materials the machine should be able to thresh at a go, the volume of the machine can be calculated thus using Equation 1:

$$v = \frac{m}{\rho} \quad 1$$

Where;

ρ = density of the rubber seed (which was determined to be 444.44 kg/m³)

V = volume of the rubber seed

M = mass of the rubber seed

Since the threshing chamber will be semi-circular, the radius of the threshing chamber can be calculated thus using Equation 2;

$$r = \sqrt{\frac{2v}{\pi h}} \quad 2$$

Where;

r = radius of the threshing chamber.

v = volume of the threshing chamber.

h = height of the threshing chamber.

$$\therefore r = \sqrt{\frac{2 \times 0.0338}{\pi \times 0.215}} = 0.316 \text{ m}$$

To allow for ease of operation, the radius of the threshing chamber was 0.35 m.

2.2.2 Threshing Arm

The average length, breadth and width of some samples of rubber seeds measured were 24, 21.33, and 19 mm. Therefore, the average dimension of rubber seeds can be thus be determined using Equation 3;

$$D_a = \frac{l+b+w}{3} \quad 3$$

Where;

l = Average length of the rubber seed

b = Average breadth of the rubber seed

w = Width of the rubber seed.

$$\therefore D_a = \frac{24 + 21.33 + 19}{3} = 21.44 \text{ mm}^3$$

The average dimension was used to determine the concave clearance (C_c) between the threshing arm assembly and the sieve which was 21.5 mm. this will just allow the seeds to be threshed

without breaking the kernel.

For ease of operation, the dimensions for the shoe on the threshing arm assembly were 200 x 50 x 35 mm with provision for points of linkage with the threshing arm. The quantity of studs on the shoes were sixteen (16) and it was distributed in such a way to allow for efficient threshing operation.

2.2.3 Concave Sieve.

The concave sieve forms the lower section of the threshing chamber and as such, the diameter of the Sieve is 700 mm. The apertures on the sieve was slot shaped with major and minor diameters since the rubber seed is irregular in shape.

Taking into consideration the average dimensions of the rubber seeds as mentioned in section 2.2.2 and the average dimensions (length breadth and width) of the kernel which was determined to be 20, 16 and 12 mm. The major and minor diameter of the sieve aperture was determined thus using Equation 4 and 5;

$$D_m = \frac{L_s + L_k}{2} \quad 4$$

Where;

D_m = Major diameter of the sieve aperture.

L_s = Length of the seed

L_k = Length of the kernel

$$\therefore D_m = \frac{24 + 20}{2} = 22 \text{ mm}$$

And,

$$D_i = \frac{W_s + W_k}{2} \quad 5$$

Where;

D_i = Minor diameter of the sieve aperture.

W_s = Width of the seed.

W_k = Width of the kernel.

$$\therefore D_i = \frac{19 + 12}{2} = 15.5 \text{ mm}$$

According to Tiwari (2015), for efficient sieving, the coefficient of open area (C_o) must be between 35 – 40 %. Using Equation 6,7 and 8 the C_o for the screen was calculated thus;

$$C_o = \frac{\text{Open area}}{\text{Total area}} \times 100 \quad 6$$

$$\text{Total area} = \frac{2\pi rh}{2} \quad 7$$

Where;

r = radius of the screen and

h = length of the screen.

$$\therefore \text{Total area} = \frac{2\pi \times 350 \times 215}{2} = \frac{472809.7}{2} = 236404.85 \text{ mm}^2$$

$$\text{Open area} = k(\pi r^2 + lb) \quad 8$$

Where;

k = Number of holes on the screen (294).

r = radius of the slot semi-circle.

l = length of the slot mid-rectangle

b = breadth of the slot mid-rectangle

$$\therefore \text{Open area} = 294((\pi \times 7.75^2) + (15.5 \times 6.5)) = 85095.92 \text{ mm}^2$$

$$\text{then } C_o = \frac{85095.92}{236404.85} \times 100 = 36 \%$$

Therefore, it satisfies the criterium for efficient sieving.

2.3 Principle of operation of the machine

The machines combine reciprocating motion and impact force to achieve the threshing of the rubber seeds. As the rubber seeds are fed to the machine, human effort is employed to drive the threshing arm assembly in a reciprocating motion which creates an impact force on the rubber seeds and threshes them. The kernel and broken shells of the rubber seeds then fall through the concave sieve and are collected at the base of the machine as represented in Plate 2. The isometric projection and parts drawing of the machine are shown in Figure 1 and 2.

Figure 1: Isometric Projection of the machine

Plate 2: Operating the machine

Figure 2: Parts drawing of the machine

2.4 Performance Evaluation of the machine.

The parameters used in evaluating the machine includes threshing efficiency, percentage of unthreshed and percentage of semi-threshed. The procedures outlined below were followed.

- i. The moisture content on wet basis of the rubber seeds was determined to be 9.307% using oven drying method as specified by ISO 665:20202 viz:

- a) Determine the initial weight of the sample before drying (B_d) as presented in Plate 3.
- b) Oven-dry the samples at 105°C as presented in Plate 4.
- c) Determine the weight of the samples intermittently on an hourly basis until an even weight is attained and record the final weight as A_d .
- d) Determine the weight of water lost (W_w) by subtracting the weight after drying (A_d) from the initial weight of the sample before drying (B_d).
- e) Use Equation 10 to determine the moisture content of the samples on wet basis.

$$\%MC_{wet\ basis} = \frac{W_w}{B_d} \times 100 \quad 9$$

Where;

$\%MC_{wet\ basis}$ = Percentage moisture content on wet basis

W_w = weight of water lost (g)

B_d = Initial weight of the sample before drying (g)

- ii. A given sample of the rubber seeds was weighed as shown in Plate 5.
- iii. The weighed sample was feed unto the machine and threshed with the time taken to thresh the rubber seeds recorded.
- iv. The threshed rubber seeds were collected and separated to threshed, unthreshed, shell and semi-threshed accordingly as shown in plate 6 before being weighed and recorded.

The performance indicators according to Reshma *et al.*, (2022) are as explained;

1. Threshing efficiency: The threshing efficiency is the fraction of seeds threshed to the materials fed by mass as percentage and can be calculated using Equation 10;

$$\text{Threshing efficiency (TE)} = \frac{M_{th}}{M_{ini}} \times 100 \quad 10$$

2. Percentage of Unthreshed: This is the ratio of the unthreshed to the fed materials in percentage as expressed in Equation 11;

$$\text{Percentage of Unthreshed (P}_{uth}) = \frac{M_{uth}}{M_{ini}} \times 100 \quad 11$$

3. Percentage of Semi-threshed: This is the ratio of the semi-threshed to the fed materials in percentage as expressed in Equation 12;

$$\text{Percentage of Semi - threshed } (P_{sth}) = \frac{M_{sth}}{M_{ini}} \times 100$$

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Plate 3: Weighing the rubber seed before Oven-drying

Plate 4: Oven-drying the rubber seeds

Plate 5: Weighing the rubber seeds to be fed to the machine

Plate 6: The performance evaluation results of the machine

3.0 Result and Discussion

The following results shown in Table 1 were obtained after the performance evaluation of the machine.

Table 1: Performance evaluation of the manual rubber seed thresher.

S/N	M _{ini} (Kg)	T _t (h)	M _{th} (Kg)	M _{sth} (Kg)	M _{uth} (Kg)	M _s (Kg)	Capacity (kg/h)	P _{uth}	P _{sth}	TE (%)
1	2	0.042	0.75	0.14	0.04	1.07	47.7	2	7	91
2	2	0.040	0.70	0.15	0.05	1.10	50	2.5	7.5	90
3	2	0.032	0.61	0.13	0.04	1.22	62.5	2	6.5	91.5
Avg							53.4	2.167	7	90.83

W_{ini} = Initial mass, T_t = time taken, W_{th} = mass of threshed seeds, W_{sth} = mass of semi-threshed seeds, M_{uth} = mass of unthreshed seeds, M_s = mass of shell, TE = threshing efficiency.

From the evaluation results, the machine displayed an excellent threshing efficiency which is between 90 – 91.5%, low unthreshed percentage ($\leq 2.5\%$) recorded indicates good sieve-concave design, shoe design and impact mechanism. The semi-threshed percentage recorded is likely due to the unevenness of the dimensions of the rubber seeds. The shells of the smaller rubber seeds just have little impact with the shoes and allows a little portion to be cracked before dropping through the sieve. The capacity of the machine (47.7 – 62.5kg/h) with human effort implies a good throughput capacity.

4.0 Conclusion

Threshing is an important post-harvest operation in rubber production process. Traditional threshing methods are tasking, laborious, time consuming and do not support large-scale operations especially for commercial purposes. Therefore, this study developed and evaluated a manual rubber seed thresher that would be affordable by farmers, easy to produce, maintain and also efficient. The machine developed exhibited an average capacity of 53.4kg/h, percentage unthreshed of 2.167 %, percentage semi-threshed of 7 % and threshing efficiency of 90.83 %.

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